
Argyle Hotel Edinburgh Value & Risk Management Assessment

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MSc. Construction Project Management

Value & Risk Management

D31VR

DECEMBER 2015

HERIOT WATT UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ENERGY, GEOSCIENCE, INFRASTRUCTURES & SOCIETY
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SUSTAINABLE BUILDING DESIGN

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1 – Introduction

The growing business in the high end leisure hotel industry is providing many commercial opportunities. The city of Edinburgh was identified as a growing market and being one of the most visited cities in Europe the demand for bedrooms is increasing every year. Our client saw this opportunity and purchased a plot in a prime location of Edinburgh near the financial exchange district in the old town at the edge of the Royal Mile and the Grassmarket. The site has privilege views from the castle and is served with the best public transportation in the city.

The client has the intention to build a high end hotel and expects to achieve a four to five stars rating. The objective of this report is to provide value, cost and risk services to our client and help the design team through the stages of the RIBA plan of work.

In order to help our client to get the most value for money in this project, our consultancy services will follow the design team through the RIBA plan of work to ensure that they develop an innovative and cost efficient design that go along with the client values, and at the same time ends on a prestigious development that can compete in this competitive market.

2 – Strategic Overview and the Project Value Drivers

2.1 – RIBA Plan of Work Stage 0 Introduction

Nowadays, good design is not a primary question of style and taste. The design of the built environment has a significant effect on many of our day-to-day life's and well design buildings can have a positive impact on people well-being, quality of life and on the economy.

At stage 0 of RIBA plan of work a project overview is needed to strategically appraise and define the project before the detailed brief is prepared. This overview introduces and explains the importance of the values drivers defined in the CABE category, and the importance that they have for the client.

The aim of this report is to explain to the design team the importance of these six categories of values, how they can help to achieve a successful design and how the investment decisions can be based on these values rather than cost.

2.2 – CABE Values Categories and Prioritisation

The Commission for Architecture and the Built Environment (CABE) was established to advise the government on architecture, urban design and public spaces in England.

The six CABE values were introduced in the client's value system in a value management workshop and by making used of the pairs comparison matrix prioritised in the following sequence: Exchange value, Use Value, Image Value, Environmental value, Social value and Cultural value.

In order to help the design team to extract the most value possible of the Argyle Hotel project, the six CABE values were introduced and explained.

2.3 – CABE Values

2.3.1 – Exchange Value

The first priority is the Exchange value, this value is the easiest to understand and the one we are most familiar. This value is translated by the commercial value of a building or the price that the market is willing to pay for. In a Hotel scenario, the exchange value can be translated in the income achieved by the hotel activities such as the number of rooms booked. To achieve the best exchange value the cost must be kept low and the financial returns maximised. The design developing can reflect this value by taking into consideration the whole life-cost of the project. Making the correct choices in the type of materials and the layout can cut the hotel running costs and maximise income. Another way is to make use of the privileged location. The Argyle hotel is situated in the city centre of Edinburgh with privileged views of Edinburgh the castle, a major tourist attraction. The maximisation of the views of the castle as well as the location can be an advantage in comparison to the competitors. The urban regeneration of this part of the city can also improve the commercial value of the building in a nearby future increasing its exchange value.

2.3.2 – Use Value

The second priority is the use value. This value is concerned with whether the building is fit for the intended purpose and the contribution it makes for the outcome values of the organisation. In the context of the Argyle Hotel it is important for the design team to take in consideration all the aspects of the design that can provide comfort for the guests and promote a pleasant work environment that inspires teamwork and communication among the hotel staff, to encourage them to provide the best customer service possible to guests. This value can be reflected in the design by making use of a clever layout that provides an easy circulation in the hotel with easy access to service areas to make daily activities simpler to staff. This layout must be easy to understand and facilitate the access to guests. The materials used and the layout must provide comfort to both guests and staff by maximising the views of the castle, natural light and ventilation and cut down the noise from the outside traffic. The materials used need to be comfortable in a way that guest fill at

home but at the same time easy to maintain, provide low maintenance costs over the life of the building, and ensure the maximum occupant satisfaction.

2.3.3 – Image Value

The third value is image value built environment has a powerful ability to present a strong visual impact. There are many cities that are associated to particular buildings, for example, the Eiffel Tower in Paris. The design of a building can also be associated with the values that an organisation wants to transmit from confidence in the future to esteem and pride. In the case of the Argyle Hotel the design needs to have the “wow” factor and be desirable for the guests. This value can be achieved by making a statement with a new and fresh design. Making use of the location with a new bold building that will change the landscape of the city centre of Edinburgh. Transforming the building into an icon of the city and take advantage of the popularity to attract guests by free advertisement in the media.

2.3.4 – Environmental Value

The fourth value is environmental value this type of value is concerned with how the impact of the building on the environment could be minimised. The construction of a building uses many natural resources and produce waste during construction. During its whole life cycle will consume vast resources such as electricity, gas and/or oil for heating and lighting for example. For the construction of a hotel is important to have the costs of these resources as low as possible since the operation runs for 24 hours. Nowadays, people are more aware of the impact of buildings in the environment and an increase on sustainable design is demanded. All these technologies can have a high capital cost but the benefits they provide if the whole life cycle of the building is taking in consideration are easily compared. To reduce the environmental impact and achieve a high environmental value, the design of the hotel should take in consideration materials that can be produced locally to reduce the carbon dioxide foot print and that are of low-maintenance to reduce the costs during the whole life cycle. The design must make use of good insulation materials as well as solar panels and geothermal heating pump to cut the consumption of

energy making the building more energy efficient. The design team must comply with the views of the castle requested by the client and at the same time be aware of the size and position of the windows, to reduce artificial light and mechanical ventilation. This last suggestion can improve the energy efficiency of the building without increasing the construction costs.

2.3.5 – Social Value

The fifth priority is social value. This value is related to how the building encourages peoples' interactions within the community and co-operate with each other to mutual understanding of the common interests. In the case of the hotels' social value can arise by minimising the impact of the construction constrains on the local community. A surveying on the local community before the design to find out what they expect from the project is important. The design team can improve social value by incorporating common interests in the urban regeneration of this part of the city to make people proud of the place they leave. If the hotel incorporates staff from the local community social value can arise by demonstrating that the hotel is committed to the wellbeing of the community.

2.3.6 – Cultural Value

The last priority is the cultural value. This value is related to the contribution a building makes to the culture of a town or city and how it relates to its location and contributes to local distinctiveness. In the case of the Argyle Hotel this value can be demonstrated by exposing the guests to the local culture. The design team can achieve this value by incorporating in the design aesthetic features from the Scottish culture but innovating in a modern design creating a high quality building leaving a legacy for future generations appreciate and fill proud of.

In order to enhance value to the project of the Argyle Hotel all the values mentioned above should be incorporated to achieve the greater value for money possible.

3 – The Project Budget

3.1 – RIBA Plan of Work Stage 1 – Project Budget

At this stage project brief needs to be completed and several significant activities need to be carried out to ensure that the next stage concept design is as productive as possible. The project budget is one of these activities. An initial order of magnitude costing or cost appraisal is made before any design is completed. This estimated cost is based on available data and past experiences of hotel projects of comparable standard.

In order to budget the Argyle Hotel several hotels build in the UK in the past decades were study and by comparing these data a final cost plan was produced.

3.1.1 – Area Schedule

Using benchmarked area data from these hotels and the AECOM Hotel Build Cost Guide it was possible to define the areas needed per room to comply with the standards of the five star hotel market. It was found that in the UK a high-end hotel bedroom has in average 36 m² and this represents a ratio to gross area of 41%. With this information and knowing that the client has a plot of land of 9000 m² and wishes to build a 170 bedroom hotel it was possible to find the gross floor area of the hotel. After this study we found that it was possible to build a larger hotel, knowing that there is a demand in the city of Edinburgh for more bedrooms. A decision of develop a 300 room hotel was made to optimise the land space and get more value for money.

The solution was a five floor building above the ground plus basement that will occupy around 50% of the plot (Table 1).

Table 1 - Area Schedule for the Argyle Hotel.

Area Schedule	
Area (m²):	26341.46
Guestrooms:	300
Gross Area/Room (m²):	87.80
Ratio Bedroom to Gross:	41%
Average Rooms Area (m²):	36.00
Number of floors	6
Foot Print Area (m²)	4,390.24
Plot Ratio Percentage	49%

Based in this preliminary area schedule, the estimated construction cost for the hotel is calculated with a cost per square meter basis.

3.2 – Benchmarks Hotels

After finding the gross floor area the cost per m² is needed. Making use of the BCIS cost models (Appendix A) and by benchmarking the same type of projects the cost/m² was found and a cost plan produced. In order to get the most accurate budget different types of hotels were benchmarked. These projects were selected in BCIS to take into account the key values driving the project. For example, an Excellent BREEAM rating hotel in London was considered to take information on costs of green technology to satisfy the environmental value. For image, social and cultural value an Architecture Grand Prix Prize winner hotel in Glasgow was selected. Two hotels with different sizes and number of rooms were selected to see how the price is related to the area. It was found that the cost/m² increases when the areas decreases. The information regarding the star rating of these hotels was corrected by visiting their websites.

Table 2 shows the relevant information in the projects benchmarked.

Table 2 - Benchmarked hotels from BCIS.

Project:	Heathrow Marriott Hotel 4		Travelodge Hotel 4 Stars		Citizen M Hotel 4 Stars		Radisson Hotel 5 Stars	
Location:	Harlington, Greater London		Aberdeenshire, Aberdeen		Southwark, London SE1		Glasgow, Strathclyde	
Area (m2):	25,309		4,008		5,929		19,047	
Guestrooms:	390		119		192		247	
Gross Area/Room (m2):	64.89		33.68		30.88		77.11	
Ratio bedroom to gross	41%		41%		41%		41%	
Rooms area (m2):	26.61		13.81		12.66		32.00	
Cost:	£34,005,340		£8,897,611		£12,575,305		£36,454,985	
Cost /m2:	£1,344		£2,220		£2,121		£1,914	
Cost Plan	Cost	Percentage	Cost	Percentage	Cost	Percentage	Cost	Percentage
1 Substructure	£1,020,160	3%	£533,857	6%	£754,518	6%	£3,280,949	9%
2 Superstructure	£10,541,655	31%	£2,847,236	32%	£7,167,924	57%	£15,311,094	42%
3 Internal Finishes	£2,040,320	6%	£533,857	6%	£377,259	3%	£1,822,749	5%
4 Fittings	£2,720,427	8%	£266,928	3%	£251,506	2%	£364,550	1%
5 Services	£10,881,709	32%	£1,868,498	21%	£2,263,555	18%	£10,571,946	29%
Total Building Cost:	£27,204,272	80%	£6,050,375	68%	£10,814,762	86%	£31,351,287	86%
6 Others*	£6,801,068	20%	£2,847,236	32%	£1,760,543	14%	£5,103,698	14%
Total cost:	£34,005,340	100%	£8,897,611	100%	£12,575,305	100%	£36,454,985	100%
Project Details:	6 storey 4 star hotel with 390 bedrooms enclosing an atrium and courtyard above 2nd floor conference and ground floor leisure facilities. RC pad and raft foundations, upper floors, roof, walls and frame; PCC stairs. Aluminium walls cladding. Asphalt roof. Double glazed aluminium windows. Block and RC partitions. Flush doors. Plaster, vinyl and paint only to walls; vinyl, carpet, marble and independent flooring; plasterboard, Artex and suspended ceilings. Bar, restaurant and leisure fittings. Bathroom pods. Fan coil heating, air conditioning, electrics. Lifts.		4 Star, 6 and 7 storey 119 bedroom hotel with basement car-park for 25 cars. RC strip foundations and slab; CFA piling. RC frame including concrete walls, upper floors and roof slab; with single membrane and standing seam aluminium cladding; Mansafe. Stairs. Ceramic Rainscreen cladding, and render external walls. Composite double glazed aluminium windows, feature windows, powered doors. Block walls, RC lift shaft and staircase walls. Internal macadam car park at ground floor. Bar furniture. Bathroom pods. Mechanical and electrical installations. Lift, Lightning protection and fire extinguishers. Fire alarms, CCTV and TV, IT distribution; televisions, music system and computer linked tills.		6 storey 4 star hotel to BREEAM rating Excellent with 192 prefabricated bedroom pods with factory installed fittings and finishes, 386m2 meeting rooms, bar/cafe and roof plant room. Piled foundations. RC slab, floors; PCC stairs. Steel frame and Kalzip metal flat roof with green roof. Stone composite, Marley Eternit cladding, St Ives block and curtain walling. Fibreglass resin and aluminium double glazed windows. Fittings. Central heating and cooling, ventilation, electrics. Lift. External works, 45m2 courtyard to centre of block, services and drainage.		8 storey, 247 bed hotel with basement fitness centre, restaurants, bars, function rooms and landscaped courtyard. Undefined foundations. Steel frame and flat roof. Curved copper cladding and glazed facade. Double glazed windows, smoked plate glass entrance. Block, brick and glazed partitions. Undefined doors. Slate, timber and tiles to walls; carpet and laminate timber flooring. Fittings. Sanitaryware. Undefined heating, ventilation, electric light and power. Lift. Kitchen/laundry equipment, TV, pool, Jacuzzi, sauna, data cabling, security. External works.	

* Others - Represent costs with preliminaries (design fees, consultancies, tender process, and etc.), external work and some contingencies. More detailed information in the Appendix 1

3.3 – Cost Plan

The hotel that most identifies with the key values driving the Argyle Hotel project is the Radisson Hotel in Glasgow. To produce the cost plan the data from this hotel was selected. For the cost/m² of the Hotels benchmarked were rebased to the 4Q 2015 and to the city of Edinburgh. The value for the cost/m² was achieved by analysing the trend that showed that the cost/m² decrease when the area increased and adding some features of green construction. So the cost/m² should be less than the Radisson Hotel but in order to enhance the environmental value some green technology must be incorporated with extra costs. Taking in consideration the rating BREEAM hotel a price in between these two hotels was found. The Argyle Hotel does not need to achieve BREEAM rating, instead just have to incorporate measures to reduce the impact on the environment and cut the running costs.

Table 3 shows the cost plane for the Argyle Hotel Edinburgh.

Table 3 - Argyle hotel Cost Plan.

Cost Plan			
Project:	Argyle Hotel 5 Stars		
Location:	Edinburgh City Centre		
Area (m²):	26341.46		
Guestrooms:	300		
Gross Area/Room (m²):	87.80		
Ratio Bedroom to Gross:	41%		
Average Rooms Area (m²):	36.00		
Cost:	£53,142,998.60		
Cost /m²:	£2,017.47		
Elements	Cost	Cost/m2	Percentage
1 Substructure	£4,589,642.80	£174.24	8.64%
2 Superstructure	£22,243,757.10	£844.44	41.86%
3 Internal Finishes	£2,432,985.39	£92.36	4.58%
4 Fittings	£367,727.14	£13.96	0.69%
5 Services	£15,236,092.31	£578.41	28.67%
Total Building Cost:	£44,870,204.74	£1,703.41	84.43%
6 Others	£8,272,793.86	£314.06	15.57%
Total cost:	£53,142,998.60	£2,017.47	100%

4 – Developing the Design and VE Application

4.1 – Developing the design at RIBA Plan of Work Stage 3

At stage three of the RIBA plan of work the concept design is further developed, the architectural design, building services and structural design are being developed in coordination with the cost information.

At this stage the client have requested a 10% cut on the budget and is requiring the best solution in order to keep the same values and quality driving the project and reduce the impact of this cut on the project. A Value Engineering (VE) study was carried out to develop solutions that go beyond traditional cost cuttings.

4.2 – Value Engineering Process

Knowing that there is a relationship between value and what we want or need and what we are willing to pay for those requirements, and since those requirements were already identified at an early stage (Value Management) the VE team knows that there was only one way to meet the cuts required by the client without major impact in the project and this way was by bringing innovation to the whole process.

A Value Engineering Workshop was put in place gathering the design team, quantity surveyors and the value engineering team to find alternatives to the existing project solutions, identify and eliminate unnecessary costs while the function and quality of the project were trying to be improved. The first stage of this VE study was to identify the high cost elements of the cost plan that represents the highest probability for value improvements and by considering the availability of material locally, construction methods, transportation issues, site limitations or restriction, and material costs to elaborate a plan to make savings. The second stage was to look at the areas schedule and knowing that the cost is a function of the area, analyse them and see if there is space for improvement.

4.3 – Elements Analysis

4.3.1 – Identification of the Higher Cost Elements

Looking at the cost plan it was determined that three major elements represent around 79% of the entire project. Superstructure with almost 42%, Services just below 29% and Substructure with approximately 9%. To achieve savings of 10% these are the elements that need to be analysed and an alternative solution needs to be developed in order to achieve the savings goal. In the cost plan, others costs represent more than 15% but are not taking into consideration in this VE study since this element is related to tendering, design and as stated above is not relating to the construction phase where VE can be affected. The Figure 1 shows the weight of each element on the cost.

Figure 1 - Weight of the Building elements on the cost.

4.3.2 – Elements Analysis and Proposals

4.3.2.1 – Superstructure

Further analyses on the element Superstructure determined that a cut of 5% can be achieved in three main sub-elements. The first is the Structural element that represents almost 16% of the cost and we expect to save 2% by reducing the span length of the columns to reduce the thickness of the slab and save on materials, as well as, bring precast solutions like stairs and the elevator shaft to reduce the labour on site. An additional 2% on the external wall that represents around 14% of the entire cost. We believe that this can be achieved by introducing precast panels similar to SIPS (Structural insulated panels), in order to reduce labour on site and insulation on the cladding system. The remaining 1% can be achieved by introducing precast open panels on the internal partition walls that represent approximately 9% of the cost. All this cost saving proposals will impact the project value and need to be concerned. In order to keep the function as much as possible and maintain the values driving the project this impact need to be identified. The proposed alteration will not affect the function of the elements chosen. The structure will keep supporting and transferring the loads, external walls will still protect the space but the changes on the structural elements can affect the image value of this project by conditioning the Architectural design. Giving limits on the layout and at the same time reduce the use value because can condense the circulation and reduce the access to service areas impacting negatively in daily activities. The changes in the external and partition walls can also affect the image value as well as the environmental value in the case of insufficient insulation. Increasing the life-costs of energy, social value can be affected if the new cladding is not according to what was agreed with the local community. If all these values are affected we can expect that our most important value, the exchange value, is going to be affected. In order to minimise the impact of these changes in the overall building project the team must make use of creative, and innovative design and materials to keep all the function that previous solutions bear.

4.3.2.2 – Substructure

Since changes on the structure of the building were made by increasing the number of columns, savings on the foundation are going to be achieved by changing the technology for a mix of pile and raft foundation. The car park in the basement is not going to be plastered and painted, and the partition wall of the services areas are going to be on painted concrete blocks and ducts of electrical and water/sewer services visible. These changes will allow saving 1% on the Substructure that represents nearly 9%. These alterations do not affect any of the functionality of the elements but could have an impact on the Image value because guests can have the feeling of entering an unfinished building. This could affect the use value by not providing a sense of comfort to guests and staff. To reduce this impact the Architect could make use of the raw materials to design a minimalistic and modern space where guests and staff can feel comfortable.

4.3.2.3 – Services

The third element identified for savings were the services that represent almost 29% of the total costs. We identified two sub-elements, the electrical installations representing approximately 9% and the HVAC system with nearly 10% and a cut of 2% in each one is going to be made. For the electrical installation the design team is going to make use of the design to reduce the cable tray and save material and labour. The HVAC system will make use of the same method and a better design on the pipeline tray and the use of new insulation foam on them will make these savings possible. These alterations do not change the function of these elements, the HVAC system will maintain the comfort and by bringing innovation to the design it was possible to save 4% in these elements. The implications of these changes on the values were considered. The possibility of these alterations in HVAC may affect the life-cost by increasing the energy consumption; affect the environmental value and the use value. The design team ensures that the impact of these measures were minimal.

4.4. – Alternative 1 – Cost Plan

Table 4 shows the new cost plan after the proposed cuts.

Table 4 - Alternative 1 – Cost Plan

Cost Plan			
Project:	Argyle Hotel 5 Stars		
Location:	Edinburgh City Centre		
Area (m²):	26341.46		
Guestrooms:	300		
Gross Area/Room (m²):	87.80		
Ratio Bedroom to Gross:	41%		
Average Rooms Area (m²):	36.00		
Cost:	£47,828,698.74		
Cost /m²:	£1,815.72		
Elements	Cost	Cost/m2	Percentage
1 Substructure	£4,058,212.82	£154.06	8.48%
2 Superstructure	£19,586,607.17	£743.57	40.95%
3 Internal Finishes	£2,432,985.39	£92.36	5.09%
4 Fittings	£367,727.14	£13.96	0.77%
5 Services	£13,110,372.37	£497.71	27.41%
Total Building Cost:	£39,555,904.88	£1,501.66	82.70%
6 Others	£8,272,793.86	£314.06	17.30%
Total cost:	£47,828,698.74	£1,815.72	100%

4.5 – Area Schedule Analyse

Another possible way to save 10% on the budget is by reducing the built area of the hotel. In the Argyle Hotel this can be achieved in three different ways. By reducing the bedroom size, increase the ratio bedroom to gross or making changes in both at the same time. These reductions in the area can be made by just reducing the area in the spaces and in this way the use and image value can be affected but the building keeps the same function. Another way is to eliminate some of these functions like the car park in the basement or the laundry room. The latter can affect the use value because the hotel has to outsource this service and could impact on the running costs. By making use of good architect practise it is possible to achieve the 10% save without affecting the key values driving the project.

4.5.1 – Alternative 2 – Cost Plan

Table 5 shows the new cost plan after the proposed cuts.

Table 5 - Alternative 2 – Cost Plan

Cost Plan						
Project:	Argyle Hotel 5 Stars		Argyle Hotel 5 Stars		Argyle Hotel 5 Stars	
Location:	Edinburgh City Centre		Edinburgh City Centre		Edinburgh City Centre	
Area (m²):	23478.26		24146.34		23611.11	
Guestrooms:	300		300		300	
Gross Area/Room (m²):	78.26		80.49		78.70	
Ratio Bedroom to Gross:	46%		41%		43%	
Average Rooms Area (m²):	36.00		33.00		34.00	
Cost:	£47,366,585.71		£48,714,415.38		£47,634,606.51	
Cost /m²:	£2,017.47		£2,017.47		£2,017.47	
Elements	Cost	Percentage	Cost	Percentage	Cost/m2	Percentage
1 Substructure	£4,090,768.58	8.64%	£4,207,172.57	8.64%	£4,113,915.94	8.64%
2 Superstructure	£19,825,957.41	41.86%	£20,390,110.67	41.86%	£19,938,141.33	41.86%
3 Internal Finishes	£2,168,530.45	4.58%	£2,230,236.60	4.58%	£2,180,800.94	4.58%
4 Fittings	£327,756.80	0.69%	£337,083.21	0.69%	£329,611.39	0.69%
5 Services	£13,579,995.32	28.67%	£13,966,417.95	28.67%	£13,656,836.86	28.67%
Total Building Cost:	£39,993,008.57	84.43%	£41,131,021.01	84.43%	£40,219,306.46	84.43%
6 Others	£7,373,577.14	15.57%	£7,583,394.37	15.57%	£7,415,300.05	15.57%
Total cost:	£47,366,585.71	100%	£48,714,415.38	100%	£47,634,606.51	100%

4.6 – Recommendations on the Project

In the highly competitive hotel market, in Edinburgh reducing the cost of 10% runs the risk of not being able to compete against other hotels. For example, the bedroom area provided in the original cost plan was greater than the hotels benchmarked providing a key difference between this development and similar hotels. Careful consideration must be taken into consideration in order to understand if these cuts are worthwhile and would not affect the position the client wants to take in this competitive market.

5 – Strategic Risk Assessment

5.1 – Risk Assessment at RIBA Plan of Work Stage 0

During the stage 0 of the RIBA plan of work the project is only at an embryonic phase where a strategic brief is prepared and the project is recognised by the client. There is the need to make some investment for a return, in this case a construction of a high end hotel located in the city centre of Edinburgh. For this reason the project can be considered as some business problem or opportunity, rather than a construction project. Only when a decision to build is made it can become a construction project. To make this decision a strategic risk assessment should be carry out to support this decision and help to ensure the project objectives are met.

5.2 – Risk in the Project Environment

The complexity associated with a construction project requires careful identification and assessment of potential risks. These risks can be classified into two main categories, external and internal. The construction environment has many stakeholders that at any time during the project will be affected in some way, either directly or indirectly, in a positive or negative way. All the stakeholders in the project are source of risk and can be categorised according to whether it emanates from the internal or external environment.

5.2.1 – Internal Environment

The internal environment is formed by the project team and supply chain. Those are represented by the numerous elements of the client organisation (employees, design team, consultants, quantity surveyor, and project manager) and the production side of the contractors, sub-contractors and suppliers. This organisation is very important and the way they perform is very important to achieve the project objectives. A failure to establish effective communication between parties, the appointment of skills and experience consultants, and a clear defined roles in the organisation can directly affect or influence the project success. The most important internal risk at

this stage is to understand what the client objectives are for the Argyle Hotel project and to avoid facing problems in the future. Since value management is intended to address this point, the biggest effort and attention is given over to value management at the early stages of the project. Although, risk should be assessed at the early stages of the project, this exercise is more likely to be carried out as part of value management than as an isolated risk study. It is only as the project progresses and the design and logistics of its delivery become an issue that risk management has a separated and defined activity on the process. Even though at this stage the focus is not at the risk it still needs to be accounted for in some way, since solutions of high value to the client will necessarily involve low, or at least known and acceptable, levels of risk.

5.2.1.1 – Recommendations to Deal with Internal Environment

The best way to deal with the risk at this stage is to collaborate with experienced consultants to appraise the business case and prepare the best strategic brief possible. Benchmark different hotels and study what the competition is offering and what is the trend in this market. It is important to explain to the client on what they can do to be one step ahead of the competition and be successful. By doing this, an initial budget according to the time and quality expected can be prepared to help the client to get the most value for money possible and take a decision on whether the investment should be put in this project or not.

A good communication strategy between client and the consultants should be put in place in order to avoid miss-understandings that could affect the project. The role of all individuals in the project and their hierarchy should be well defined to facilitate the communications.

5.2.2 – External Environment

The external risks are outside the control of the project team and the host organisation. The external risks are generally more difficult to predict and control. Factors such as physical external environment and other events may directly impact

the project's effectiveness. Some risk may be difficult to foresee such as political, social and economic environment. This kind of event directly threatens the project, but often takes project managers by surprise.

Some of these risks are more critical at different stages of the project but still need to be accessed at this stage for a better decision on the viability of the project. For example the physical external environment can affect the project during the construction phase; the cold winter of Edinburgh can affect the progress of the works on site and create delays on the open day. At this stage the client just needs to be informed and be aware of these possibilities.

At this stage a more prominent external risk is the economic environment. Economy has different cycles and can be difficult to forecast. A construction of a hotel with these characteristics can take about two years to complete, changes in the interest of inflation and taxation rates can have multiple impacts on projects and jeopardise its success.

Another major external risk at this stage is the political and social risk. The impact that the hotel has on the external environment can create obstacles on the approval of the project. The plot is located near the castle, one of the most touristic places in the city, and near the commercial and business district. The constraints with the resultant noise and light pollution and disruption to access in local streets can affect the neighbours creating obstacles on the project. And since the plot is located at an historic part of the city, local legislation and construction regulation can affect the project.

5.2.2.1 – Recommendations to Deal with External Environment

The external risks are difficult to predict and control but awareness of the possibilities of happening can help to mitigate or better manage the risk. At this stage the consultant team must be aware of the local planning regulations and legislation for the construction of the hotel. It also needs to identify all the external stakeholders in order to predict which ones could affect negatively the project. A meeting with the local county council to show the intention of building a hotel is important to receive and analyse the feedback on the project.

The client should take in consideration a contingency plan for possible deviations on the budget due to economic constrains or unexpected problems. Insurance should be contracted in order to anticipate losses from these problems.

5.3 – Recommendations on the Project

There is a strong business opportunity to be made taking into account the excellent location of the plot and the growing demand for rooms in the city of Edinburgh. The risk will always be present in the project but if well managed it is possible to be successful. We recommend that the client should commit to the project and proceed to the next stage.

6 – Risk Control and Construction

6.1 – Risk at RIBA Plan of Work Stage 5 (Construction)

It is at this stage of the RIBA plan of work that the risk is more prominent. The construction phase brings many uncertainties. If poorly managed the complex framework of individuals with different commercial expectations could affect the cost and the work programme. The nature of the works is also exposed to hazards and more than commercial losses this class of risks can result in physical damages, injuries or death. Experience in construction shows that some risks can be predictable and managed. In all projects a risk management process should be implemented to identify, analyse and give response to the risk. These processes allow to avoid and to mitigate some of these risks.

6.2 – Risk Register

A risk register is a very useful tool in the risk management process, enables risks to be listed and tracked through the life of the project. By listing these risks it would make it easier to take corrective actions to reduce its impacts on the project.

For the Argyle Hotel a risk register was prepared (Appendix B) and the top five risks that the project faces at this stage were identify and described below (Table 6). Associated control measures were put in place to deal with these risks.

Table 6 - Top five risks

Top Five Risks		
Title	Detailed Description	Control Measure
Site Ground Conditions	<p>The plot is located at city centre of Edinburgh where an old Building was demolish it is possible to find:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remaining's of the old building within excavated areas; • Unknown contamination with asbestos or hazards material within excavated areas; • Existing services to be maintained and also a number of new diversions during the works. • Damage to adjacent buildings within excavated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intensive surveying and investigation of the plot to identify and trace all the possible problems; • Create procedures on site to deal with this constrains effectively to prevent delays for example survey team on site with framework and authority to approve variations; • Contingency on the budget to face possible overruns.
Site Logistic Restrictions	<p>Due to the city centre location logistical problems may arise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constrains on the delivery of materials on site due to restrictions on the size and load transported; • Insufficient space to store material and equipment's on site; • Restrictions on the use of equipment's example tower cranes; • Restriction on the work hours do to noise and light pollution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check the viability of space for shipyard on site; • Let a shipyard outside the city to store equipment's and material; • Plan the material and equipment's needed on site at different stages to avoid useless material and equipment's on site; • Divide transportation of materials in smaller transportation to avoid disruptions to neighbours and local traffic; • Plan work activities in order to avoid disruptions to neighbours;
Design Changes	<p>Changes in design and requirements made throughout the construction phase can affect the programme and cost. Late drawings and instructions, defective design resulting in interferences between activities, poor level of detail.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require the design team to create the project in BIM environment in order for the client to better understand the project and avoid changes. Use this environment to check interferences among all specialities (structural, water supply etc.); • Create procedures to trace drawing to avoid work with superseded drawings; • Create procedures for drawing approvals with time scale.
Health and Safety	<p>The nature of the works are expose to hazards that can cause physical impacts or health consequences on people:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Earthmoving, excavation and trench works; • Activities at high heights; • Exposure to heavy equipment's and materials; • Crane operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create procedures for the health and safety environment with CDM regulations; • Provide the adequate protection equipment's to staff; • Provide training on health and safety to staff; • Provide equipment's and materials hazards handling sheets; • Create a health and safety risk assessment for all the work activities on site with control measures; • Contract with adequate insurance to cover possible accidents.
Lack of Communication	<p>Poor communication between all the parties involved in the process can result in delays and cost overruns as well as in disputes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor communication between: • Project Manager and client; • Project manager and design team; • Project manager and contractor; • Contractor and subcontractors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a frame work with a clear job role of all the intervenient in the project with clear hierarchy; • Create communication channels with weekly or daily meetings and make use of the new technology to share and update information; • Incorporate NEC3 ECC standard form of contract to promote collaboration between the parties involved in the contract.

7 – Conclusion

This report explains that the value and risk management are an iterative process and should be carried out during all phases of the project. At different stages they might have different importance and impact on the project. On an early stage value management studies should be performed in order to identify and explain to the client values while risk has a more prominent relevance during the construction phase. In order to achieve success and deliver the most value for money to the client, this iterative process should be prepared at an early stage and revisited and improved during the whole duration of the plan of work.

Appendix A – Cost Plans from BCIS

Appendix B – Schedule of Technical Risks

Schedule of Technical Risks						
Project Name Stage				Pre Control		
				Likelihood	Impact	Score / RAG
Title		Detailed Description				
1	Site Ground Conditions	Inadequate information about ground conditions		4	4	Red
2	Site Logistic Restrictions	Restrictions on the access to site		3	4	Red
3	Design Changes	Changes in design and requirements made throughout the construction phase		3	4	Red
4	Programme Delays	Programme delays caused by lack of information and unforeseen events		3	3	Yellow
5	Poor Performance of the Contractor	Contractor selection and performance with contractor having insufficient resources to tackle the type of project		2	3	Yellow
6	Human Resources	Not having the right people for the job		2	3	Yellow
7	Lack of work scope Definition	Lack of defined scope of works at the outset of construction with areas of design incomplete		3	3	Yellow
8	Health and Safety	Health and safety, accidents in the work place, and occupational health		4	4	Red
9	Budget Overrun	Cost overruns caused by poor estimating, poor communication, and insufficient pre-planning		3	3	Yellow
10	Statutory Approval Delays	Approval delays from local authorities		3	3	Yellow
11	Coordination Between Main and Sub-contractors	Coordination of responsibilities between specialist contractors and the main contractor		3	3	Yellow
12	Quality of Management Control	Quality of management control		3	3	Yellow
13	Insufficient Design Information	Inadequacy and availability of design information		3	3	Yellow
14	Delays in the Supply Chain	Fragmentation of supply chain – site deliveries not to schedule		3	4	Red
15	Lack of Communication	Poor communication between all the parties involved in the process		3	4	Red
16	Cash flow	Delays on payments resulting in delays in the programme		3	3	Yellow
17	Uncontrollable Events	External Physic environment (weather conditions)		2	3	Yellow
18	Consent and Approvals	Consent and Approvals dealing with changes during construction		3	3	Yellow
19	Economical Changes	Changes in interest rates and inflation		2	4	Yellow
20	Environmental Issues	Contamination of the environment with hazard materials		2	2	Green